

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS UNDER DIGITAL CONDITIONS

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Abstract. Currently, various pedagogical information-educational resources have been created in electronic form in educational institutions, but the research on creating the organizational basis for their use cannot be considered sufficient.

Keywords: digitization, professional communication, Crossword Forge, iSpring QuizMaker, Internet, information.

Today, all educational institutions pay special attention to the use of innovative technologies in the educational environment in order to ensure that students receive knowledge in accordance with modern requirements.

Among the options available in Crossword Forge, it is worth noting the ability to access dictionaries of different languages to help you find the exact word in the crossword, the ability to choose different graphical aspects for presenting crosswords, and the functions of printing and exporting it. The finished puzzle can be exported as Text, PDF, image or web view [1].

Crossword Forge offers you the ability to create other games such as word search games for kids and adults.

1 958 KB) [1 / 1] 91% **Fizik boshqotirma**

Download Crossword Forge and enjoy creating your own crosswords with different looks and content!

Features of iSpring QuizMaker: Questionnaire a new test type. Questionnaire-type questions have correct answers, and all tests can be supplemented with additional information slides that provide additional explanations. A new type of question: 10 questionnaire questions and a question with an evaluated "Active field". They serve to obtain information from the user. Add formulas to questions. Microsoft Equation Editor (included in Microsoft Office) must be enabled to use this feature. Pictures and formulas can also be placed in the answer options. True/false information can be set separately for each question. Ability to add branching functionality. The ability to adjust the way to pass the test depending on the correct answers [2].

The ability to configure the display of test results depending on the success or failure of the assigned tests. Ability to export the test to Word. Ability to print results. New interface of iSpring QuizMaker. Ability to change text font size, style and colors for question text and notes, text alignment, bulleted lists and paragraphs. A new type of media content - flash files - to add

concepts to questions. Ability to display points for each answer in single-choice and multiple-choice questions. Ability to automatically create a backup copy of tests [3]. The ability to customize the template of test results reports. Choose whether to display a test pass when publishing to distance learning systems. Ability to limit the number of test attempts from 1 to 10.

Getting Started: Start iSpring QuizMaker and you will see the "Working" window on the screen. This window allows you to create a new evaluative test or questionnaire, open a test, import a test. This dialog allows you to provide technical support for iSpring QuizMaker web resources and purchase software [4].

The first interface of the Ispring Quiz Maker module: The program differs from other electronic quiz creation programs with the following features:

- the working file of the program can be copied to any computer and run;
- very few actions are performed;
- no special knowledge is required;
- 13 different types of tests can be created;
- pictures, formulas and videos can be placed on test questions and answers;
- test results are sent directly to e-mail;
- that the program is licensed and open-key [5].

After installing the iSpring Suite software package on the computer, it is possible to create electronic tests using the Ispring Quiz Maker block. After the test database is created, the number of tests and the test time are determined depending on which part of the lesson they will be used for. The appearance of the interface can be changed at the discretion of the user. After creating a database of ready-made tests, it is possible to save it for the local network, for the global network, in document form (MS Word) or for the LMS system [6]. The working file of the database of electronic tests created in the program is saved in *.swf format. So, to use this database of tests, it is enough to have Adobe Flash Player on the computer. The following views of test questions can be created in the program:

1. Single answer test: the difficulty of this test depends on the number of answer options.
2. Multiple-choice test: with the help of this type of test, it is possible to determine the student's opinion on several pieces of information.

3. "True-false" type of test: in this type of test corresponding to the form of the questionnaire question, there are only two answer options;
 4. "Short answer" test: the test taker must enter a one-character short answer in the text field;
 5. Ranking of answers: in this type of question, the answer options are ranked among themselves;
 6. Matching: several questions are combined with their answers;
 7. Enter a number: as an answer to the question, the student must enter a number;
 8. Fill in the blanks: it is required to fill in one or more blanks in the text with the required word;
 9. The question with the answers: in the empty parts of the question, the answer options are given, you can choose the correct one from these answer options.
 10. Word bank: Select the necessary words from the given words and place them in the empty spaces of the text. To make the question more difficult, the number of words can be increased by the number of blank spaces.
 11. Question identifying the active area: The task of defining an area in the picture is placed in the question, and the area in this picture is selected by the student in the process of answering.
 12. Essay: The test-taker must write an extended response (essay) to the given topic.
- Creating a test:* After starting the iSpring QuizMaker program, you will see the "Start" window on the screen. It is possible to create a new test or questionnaire, open a recently created test.

You can also create a new test using the main menu:

1. Click on the QuizMaker logo located at the top left of the main window.
2. Select Create new test from the resulting menu.
3. Choose the type of test: Evaluative or questionnaire (Оцениваемый тест or Questionnaire).

The database of tests created above shows that this test will be less uniform and more interesting for students than traditional tests. In addition, the possibility of enriching these interactive tests with the help of pictures, sounds and videos makes them more interesting and encourages the student to work with great enthusiasm. The use of simple tests creates a certain limit in the formulation of questions [7,8,9].

Teachers of other subjects, such as mathematics, biology, geography, are also very interesting, there is an opportunity to create an interactive test.

In addition, the possibility of conducting the test through computer networks and the possibility of sending it by e-mail can also meet the requirements of modern education.

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